

DEVELOPING MICROCONTROLLER SCHEMATIC SYSTEMS BY USING PROTEUS ENVIRONMENT

Javlon Tursunov,

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, javlontatu96@mail.ru

Gulrukh Memonova,

Karshi branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, memonova1990@mail.ru

Annotation: In this article, the structure of the microcontroller system in the PRATEUS program is studied using the specific features and characteristics of modern microcontrollers. Considerations on creation of microcontroller-based systems and improvement of its development are also presented.

Key words: Microcontroller, PRATEUS, analog, digital, librar,circuit, multichannel.

Writing software for microcontrollers provides greater cost savings in the design of primary and secondary devices, as well as a number of opportunities for developing small and convenient control devices that meet modern requirements. For example, various sensors play an important role in the development of temperature, humidity and gas analyzers, as well as in the programming of microcontrollers for transmitting and receiving signals. Programming of microcontrollers is carried out using many programming languages and various environments. One such environment is the PRATEUS environment, which is a computer program that combines Labcenter Electronics' SPICE system for modeling electronic devices with the ability to create designs based on animated components

and microcontrollers. The program includes modern microcontrollers: PIC, 8051, AVR, HC11, ARM7 / LPC2000 and other common processor models.

The software library also contains more than 6,000 models of analog and digital devices, while the library is updated with new models from manufacturers and users. This system works with many compilers and programming languages. With PROTEUS, you can simultaneously tune several complex microcontrollers of different types, correcting their shortcomings. The Proteus program consists of two main parts: ISIS and ARES.

ISIS is a graphical schematic diagram editor designed to enter data into the project being created and transfer data to the ARES program to prepare a circuit board based on this circuit diagram.

ARES is a graphics editor for printed circuit boards. This software has ELECTRA modules that automatically place and automatically connect components and check electrical circuits.

That is, as mentioned above, once the schematic diagram of the designed device is ready in ISIS, we can use the ARES program to prepare the seal board by automatically placing the components and automatically connecting them.

One of the microcontroller-based control devices is the formation of an analog-to-digital converter using the Rpoteus environment.

As for analog-to-digital converters (ADCs), they take analog input signals and generate digital signals suitable for processing on microprocessors and other digital devices.

Figure 1. Proteus Desktop.

The analog-to-digital converter is multichannel and is included in modern models of AVR microcontrollers. The meaning of multichannel is that an analog multiplexer is installed at the input of the analog-to-digital converter.

It can be connected to different outputs of the MCU to measure multiple unrelated analog values with time accuracy. The multiplexer input can be used alone or (on some models) combined in pairs to measure differential signals.

In some cases, an A/D converter provides additional options when combined with a voltage amplifier with a gain of 10 and 200. Below, an A/D converter from the Proteus environment using the ADC0804 device is illustrated.

First, we access the Proteus environment from the desktop to the library and move the required devices to the Proteus desktop. For the A/D Converter, select the following tools (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Tool kit (ADC0804, BUTTON CERAMIC15P, LED-RED, MINRES10K, POT-HG).

Then we connect them to the ADC0804 in Proteus8, then after the connection subsequently pressing the start (Figure 3).

Figure 3. A/D converter activation status.

As we can see, the above circuit accepts analog input signals and accordingly generates corresponding digital signals for processing on digital devices. The development of modern science and technology requires the development of various fields.

This Proteus8 environment serves to expand the theoretical and practical knowledge of industry professionals through virtual software development and physical processes in the development of various industries, as well as the development and implementation of devices based on various microcontrollers.

References

1. Й.В. Новиковю, “Основи микропроцессорной техники”, Учебное пособие. ХХИ 2008.
2. Лебедев М.Б. СодеВисионАвр: Пособие для начинающих. М.: «Додека-ХХИ», 2008.
3. Й.В. Новиков, Основы микропроцессорной техники. Учебное пособие. Москва: ИНТУИТ, 2009.
4. Ramesh Chopra, “Microcontroller Based Project”, EFY Enterprises PVT Ltd, 2010
5. Ж.Й.Юнусов, Х.Й.Абасхонова Рақамли қурилмалар ва микропроцессор тизимлари. Ўқув Қўлланма Тошкент-2010-бет.

6. PROTEUS DESIGN SUITE, Getting Started Guide, 2019
7. www.ZiyoNET.uz - Information and educational portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
8. www.labcenter.com
9. www.proteus123.narod.ru
10. www.FlowCode6 .
11. http://www.labkit.ru/html/Assembler_for_PIC.MPLAB
12. www.Atmel.com